

**THE FORMATION OF CIVIL LAW REGULATION OF
DIGITAL RIGHTS**

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Annotation

This scientific article describes the importance of civil law regulation of digital rights, the relationship of digital law with other rights, civil law analysis of digital law, theoretical and practical problems of the introduction of digital rights as a special object in civil circulation, conducted comparative analysis of the conceptual foundations for determining the rights and obligations of subjects of digital law, as well as scientific meta-methodological foundations of the categorization of digital rights in civil law.

Keywords: digital law, digital rights, information technologies, digitization digital civil law, property rights, civil law regulation of information, personal data.

Civil law regulation of information, information technologies, information systems, as well as information activities forms the main body of norms in the field of information legislation. Changes in the current legislation aimed at the development of the digital environment do not always allow us to unambiguously define the basic idea of the law-making process. This circumstance has a negative impact on the sequence of development of legislation in the field under consideration, leading to lagging regulation and the preservation of legal gaps. We believe that the reason for this problem is the lack of an integral and self-sufficient concept that would allow more effectively focusing the efforts of the scientific community and practitioners in the field of developing mechanisms for regulating digital information, taking into account the emerging realities and emerging trends in the modern information society.

As noted in scientific research, definitions serve as the constructive basis of the concept [1]. Definitions are derived through the use of formal logic techniques, and the rules of legal technique form the basis for a uniform understanding of new categories and direct interpretation of norms. Accordingly, the development of the concept involves the formulation of definitions in key subject areas.

If the concept of information as a subject area of the science of information law is not only widely doctrinally developed, but also legislatively formulated, then definitions for emerging phenomena and facts that have the nature of a connecting link and reflect trends in the development of legal relations require additional theoretical elaboration and interpretation within the framework of scientific research. It is difficult to attribute the phenomenon of digitalization and its derivatives to such a category. Such categories, as a rule, are abstract and therefore do not require regulatory consolidation for quite understandable reasons. Firstly, digitalization captures in consciousness and embodies only a collective image of all social processes taking place in a given period of time, due to the level of development of digital communication channels and the penetration of information technologies into the domestic sphere and legal practice. Secondly, it can be assumed that digitalization will eventually be replaced by another phenomenon, in which another object (for example, a robot) will become predominant or a subject area (for example, quantum technologies).

The main obstacles to the derivation and interpretation of definitions related to information and information technologies in the context of digitalization are the lack of uniform regulatory specification. As a rule, the legislator tends to appeal to already existing structures, saving legal tools. The lack of concepts and definitions for new categories leads to practical difficulties in the process of legal activity [2].

On June 3, 2016, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Resolution No. 188 "On measures to continue the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Government" [3]. The document was adopted as part of the implementation of the law "on electronic Government", the Regulations on the procedure for providing electronic public services through the Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services and official websites of state bodies, on the government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Internet were approved, amendments and additions were made to some government resolutions.

The document defines such tasks as preventing unnecessary interference in the process of providing public services in electronic form, reducing the number of documents and requests required from the public and business, simplifying the process of providing services, as well as bringing documents of state bodies into a single form.

Using the example of foreign legislation regulating the confidentiality of personal information (personal data) and their protection, it is possible to

clearly notice differences in national regulation, understanding of categories and applied approaches. At the same time, new methods and ways of working with data are becoming ubiquitous, which makes it possible to form the basis for many processes in the global information society. The practice and results of the development of digitalization are closely related to the boundaries of information activity, which are outlined by the norms of law.

For example, in Switzerland, personal data refers to information related to an identified or identifiable person, it consists of religious, ideological, political, professional views, occupation, health status, personal life and race, social support measures received, facts of administrative and criminal liability [4]. The volume of confidential personal data protected by law in Malaysia can be expanded due to by-law regulation, but their core is formed by information about the physical and mental health and condition of a person, political views and religious beliefs, facts of bringing a person to justice [5]. The Japanese national regulation does not detail the content of personal information, noting that this information should relate to a living person who can be identified thanks to them (name, date of birth and other information about the person that allows him to be identified) [6]. In New Zealand, the definition of personal data is not legally fixed, however, depending on the methods of their use and processing, it is possible to distinguish their volume and content [7].

Different regulation in national jurisdictions leads to different results in practice. The example with confidential information helps to establish how much information remains protected, and to what extent the data can be processed using information technologies in a particular national jurisdiction. The formation of uniform and universal rules in the information space is not always possible, which is due not only to legal reasons, but also to political, economic, social, cultural and other factors.

Among the main risks for building an integrated approach to the regulation of digital information can be identified:

- software stability and fault tolerance of systems;
- the variety of technologies and systems used;
- the emergence of information systems with intellectual functions that do not require human participation in the implementation of information activities;
- an increasing number of subjects of information activity.

Taking into account the above, two key aspects can be identified, which reveal the features of digitalization necessary for the implementation of timely legal regulation. Firstly, the digitalization of the legal system increases the availability

of legal information. It removes barriers in receiving and perceiving information. The implementation of certain actions by obtaining information occurs consciously, which allows a more optimal approach to the choice of a behavior model in accordance with already known rules. Secondly, the digitalization of the legal system is designed to provide legal regulation of public relations in a virtual environment. Due to the possibility of carrying out legally significant actions in the new environment, the need for their recognition and giving them a special status, and therefore in the settlement of relations, is formed. At the same time, the recognition of the environment, namely the permissibility of using a specific information system and actions in it, is provided by authorized state bodies or the legislator. The request for regulation is subject to satisfaction in relations of the most diverse plan, and they may quite obviously fall under the regulation of various branches of law, but a basic understanding of this need is formed and developed in the information law system.

Digital information is characterized by several key features that allow it to be isolated as an independent category for the development of a system of legal regulation:

- distribution without the use of a carrier (the need for a carrier is to ensure the conditions for storing information);
- transformation into the necessary format, possible for perception and use through the use of information technology (the ability to ensure universal compatibility of information);
- wide opportunities for transmission and distribution through digital communication channels;
- receipt by a specific person (the addressee of the communication is determined);
- increasing the dynamics of information exchange and the development of turnover, as well as the impact on the emergence, change and termination of legal relations.

In the modern information society, digital information is important for most spheres of human activity. Its main purpose is to meet the information and other needs of subjects of public relations. For the legal system, such information is of particular importance, since it accelerates the development of social processes related to information exchange and actual turnover. The digital economy is the next stage of social development, in which digital information and information technologies receive priority. Consequently, it may be necessary to develop a

more rapid system of legal regulation for relations, the subject of which is digital information in certain areas of activity.

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